

EFFECT OF POLYAMIDE VEIL LAYER ON STRENGTH PROPERTY OF VARTM CFRP

Y. Yoshida^{1*}, Y. Hirano², Y. Iwahori², Y. Kogo¹

¹ Dept. of Materials sci. and tech, Tokyo University of Science, 264-1 Yamazaki Noda, Chiba, Japan,

² Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency, 6-13-1 Osawa, Mitaka, Tokyo, Japan

* Corresponding author (j8210658@ed.noda.tus.ac.jp)

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1 Introduction

In recent years, advanced composite materials have been widely used in aerospace structures since their specific strength and stiffness are higher than those of currently used aerospace metals. The application can therefore result in weight saving, hence an improved fuel consumption rate and composites also promise lower maintenance cost. However, the production cost of composites structures is higher than that of metal ones. Therefore, low-cost processing methods, such as vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM), have attracted attention [1]. This molding process reduces manufacturing cost because it does not require expensive equipment and materials, such as an autoclave and prepregs. On the other hand, it does have some drawbacks; strength decrease, quality loss and dimensional instability as a result of the low pressure applied during the process. In the past, several studies have reported the effect of process parameters on the strength properties and molding quality [2], [3]. In case the application of CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastic) in aircraft structures, one of the issues is the large residual strength degradation after impact, after for instance bird strikes or fallen tools during maintenance. Therefore, compression after impact (CAI) characteristics usually governs the practical strength design of composite principal structures. Thus, improving this CAI strength is desirable approach to reduce the structural weight. One of the approaches is that adding thermoplastics into matrix resin of laminate. This study intends to achieve high performance CFRP produced by the VaRTM process, F statistical test focuses on CAI strength is applied to investigate the effects of VaRTM process and inserting polyamide (PA12) veil in between carbon layers by performing .

2 Experimental

2.1 Material and cure process

In VaRTM the carbon fiber preforms are impregnated with liquid resin using only vacuum (Fig.1). The CFRP laminates are composed of quasi-isotropic non crimp fabric (NCF) preforms that are stitched with thermoplastic fibers, and epoxy resin. The applied carbon fibers are IMS 60 (Toho Tenax) and the used resin is XNR/HNR 6809 (Nagase ChemteX Co., Ltd.).

The resin temperature was kept at 40°C and vacuumed for degassing from 30 to 60 minutes before resin impregnation. During a resin impregnation process, perform temperature also was kept at 40°C. Then the resin was impregnated with the preform by vacuuming at -98kPa. After resin impregnation, the preform was cure at 80°C for 16 hours as first cure, then temperature was rise up to 120°C and kept at 2 hours for as post cure. Dimensions of molded products are 330mm (width) × 330mm (length) × 3.9~6.0mm (thickness).

Table 1 shows the preprocessing conditions. All dry preform were treated with hot compaction before resin impregnation. In the case of hot compaction without hot pressing the laminates have been exposed to 80°C for two hours at atmospheric pressure. The ones with hot pressing were exposed to +20 atm and 180°C for 15 minutes. In the case of included polyamide (PA-12) layers, these were inserted in between the carbon fiber NCFs before hot compaction process.

Fig.1 Schematic of VaRTM process

Table 1 Preprocessing conditions

No.	Hot compaction conditions	PA-12
01	1atm, 80°C	N/A
02	1atm, 80°C	Applied
03	+20atm, 180°C	N/A
04	+20atm, 180°C	Applied

2.2 Measurement of molding quality and strength property

Molding quality was assessed by measurement of the fiber volume fraction (V_f) by JIS (Japanese Industry Standard) K 7075 which is combustion method (This method is compatible with ASTM D 3171.). The size of specimens are 8mm (width) \times 8mm (length). The compression strength was determined by doing NHC (ASTM D 6641) and CAI (ASTM D 7136 and 7137) tests. The size of specimens of NHC test are 12mm (width) \times 140 (length) and CAI test are 100mm (width) \times 150mm (length). For the CAI test, a drop-weight impact machine was used to damage the specimens (Fig.2); the impact energy was 6.7 J/mm. Extent of the applied damage was evaluated using non-destructive inspection (NDI) technique which is ultrasonic testing. Compression machine used in NHC and CAI tests was the Instron 4482 and 5589; crosshead speed was 1.00 mm/min. The number of specimen is $n=4$, $n=6$, and $n=3$ for V_f , NHC, and CAI test, respectively.

Fig.2 Out-of-plane drop-weight impact machine

2.3 Analysis of variance

It is intended that significance of effect of focused factor, varied manufacturing process, on mechanical properties or manufacturing quality is determined; the results of each test were tested by F-test which is one of the statistical hypothesis testing. F-test can be obtained F-value and p-value. F-value is determined greatness of effect of focused factor. P-value is determined significance of effect of focused factor. As a result of F-test, if p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This study focused on effect of hot compaction conditions and polyamide.

3 Results and discussion

Fig.3 shows the result of measurements of V_f . The figure shows that for the hot pressed laminates, V_f with polyamide veils is as high as V_f without polyamide veils. For the laminates without hot pressing on the other hand, the addition of polyamide veils results in a lower V_f . Glass-transition temperature (T_g) of polyamide veil is 50°C, and melting point is 176°C. Thus, the heating to 180°C during hot compaction melts the polyamide veils, which will consequently adhere to fibers. Consequently, carbon fiber layers were stayed in densely by this adhesion, and this reduces the required amount of resin, resulting in the same V_f as without polyamide veils.

Fig.3 Comparison of measured V_f

Layer of polyamide 100µm

Fig.5 Cross-sectional observation result of No.4

Layer of polyamide 100µm

Fig.4 Cross-sectional observation result of No.2

Fig.4 shows cross-sectional observation result of No.2 (80°C, 1atm, with polyamide). In Fig.4, the polyamide layer which did not melt remained a form of veil can be observed. In the case of the heating to 80°C during hot compaction, the heating to 80°C is not sufficient to melt the polyamide veil, so they are extraneous layers in the laminate resulting in a lower V_f . Fig.5 shows cross-sectional observation result of No.4 (180°C, +20atm, with polyamide). In Fig.5, the polyamide layer which melted adhered to the fiber can be observed.

Focus on the void content, Fig.6 shows the result of measurements of void content. The figure shows that for the hot pressed laminates (No.3 and 4), void content was increased. In case of the laminates with polyamide veils (No.2 and 4), the variation in void was reduced.

Fig.6 Comparison of measured void content

It is considered that the reason why hot-pressed laminate shows the larger void content is the hot-press process makes closer gap between carbon fibers and it traps smaller bubbles compared to not hot-pressed case. The reason why the polyamide added laminate shows larger variance of void content is considered that the application of polyamide can equalize interlaminar void content. However, void content was indirectly measured by using combustion method. In this method, void content is calculated by subtracting V_f and resin contents from total volume of composite; its include the content of polyamide inclusion. Thus, for detail discussion for void content, more precise measurement such as acid solution process should be performed.

Fig.7 shows the obtained NHC strength. Fig.8 and Fig.9 shows the obtained CAI strength and damage area. It can be observed that the NHC strength is decreased with the addition of polyamide veil in both No.2 and 4. In case of No.2, as shown in Fig.4, polyamide veils which remained as foreign material in between adjacent NCFs. This would become the origin of fracture and resulting in decrease of strength property. In case of No.4, as shown in Fig.5, polyamide veils well melted and it would not become the origin of fracture. Therefore, compared with the results with hot pressed and without polyamide veil (No.3), melted polyamide veil was hardly affect on the compression strength property.

For the CAI test, the hot pressed laminate including polyamide veils shows a higher strength than the others specimens. If the polyamide veils are inserted but the laminate is not hot-pressed, the strength is lower than without the veils. Fig.10 (a)~(d) shows results of NDI for No.1, 2, 3, and 4.

As shown in the result, insertion of polyamide veil can reduce damaged area effectively. In case of No.4, polyamide veils were melt-infiltrated into inside of matrix resin. This result suggests that not only interlaminar toughness but also toughness of through-thickness direction is enhanced, this reduced damage area by impact. The result shows that the CAI strength of No. 2 is lower than that of No.1. As shown in the Fig.4 polyamide remains as veil between CNF's without hot-press process (NO. 2). This fact indicates though inserting polyamide veil without hot-press reduce the damage area, CAI strength is also reduced. Comparing the result of No.1 and No.3 (laminates without polyamide veil), hot-pressed laminate, No. 3, shows lower CAI strength than No.1. Difference between these process conditions is hot-press condition and resulting V_f . Therefore, it is considered that the resin rich layer in inter-layer increases resistance against delamination propagation.

Fig.7 Comparison of NHC strength

Fig.9 Comparison of damage area

Fig.8 Comparison of CAI strength

(a) preforming condition: 80°C, 1atm

(b) preforming condition: 80°C, 1atm, PA12

(c) preforming condition: 180°C, +20atm

(d) preforming condition: 180°C, +20atm, PA12
Fig.10 Result of NDI

In order to analyze an effect of varied manufacturing process on the mechanical properties, F-test was performed. As focused factor, for V_f , void content, NHC strength, and CAI strength, hot compaction conditions (A), presence or absence of polyamide veil (B), and interaction effect of A and B ($A \times B$) were assigned. The factor and level of each factor are provided in Table 2 and the results of F-test are shown in Table 3.

Focus attention on V_f , one of the molding qualities, main effect A (hot compaction conditions) showed a higher F-value than the other main effects, and the p-value was less than 0.05. Consequently, it is showed that hot compaction conditions are the most influencing factor on V_f variation. Other main effects showed lower F-value than main effect A but these p-values also were less than 0.05. This result shows main effects B and $A \times B$ also have an influence.

Table 2 Factor and level for F-test

Factor / Level	1	2
A: Hot compaction conditions	1atm 80°C	+20atm 180°C
B: PA-12	N/A	Applied

Table 3 Result of F-test

Factor	V_f (N=4)		Void (N=4)	
	F	p	F	P
A	273.930	<0.05	30.787	<0.05
B	33.909	<0.05	0.181	0.678
$A \times B$	35.107	<0.05	7.329	<0.05
Factor	NHC (N=6)		CAI (N=3)	
	F	p	F	P
A	0.111	0.743	0.254	0.628
B	36.569	<0.05	6.467	<0.05
$A \times B$	14.711	<0.05	22.920	<0.05

As with V_f , it is showed that hot compaction conditions are the main influencing factor of void content. Similarly, inserting polyamide wasn't accepted as an influencing factor on void content. But for main effect $A \times B$ it was accepted as an influencing factor of void content. These result explained that the molding condition is significantly affected by changing the hot compaction conditions.

Focus attention on NHC strength, F-value of main effect A was less than 1.0, p-value was more than 0.05; null hypothesis of main effect A was not rejected. On the other hand, main effect B showed the highest F-value and p-value was less than 0.05; the null hypothesis was rejected, i.e., presence or absence of polyamide veil is the main influence factor on NHC strength.

In case of CAI strength, the null hypothesis of main effect a (preforming process) wasn't rejected though that of main effect B (with or without polyamide veil) and interaction of A and B was rejected. The influence factor on CAI strength is B and interaction of A and B. The result shows that the interaction of A and B has largest effect on CAI strength because they show the highest F-value. This result suggested that there is another factor effect on the CAI strength.

By using F-test method, effectiveness of factor (parameter) which controls the manufacturing

quality and strength can be examined. After judged the factor, appropriate condition for each factor would be able to chosen. However, for CAI strength, additional examination is required to determine the most effective factor.

4 Conclusions

The effect of the VaRTM process on the molding quality and compression strength has been made clear by determining the fiber volume fraction and performing CAI and NHC strength tests.

The CAI test clearly shows the increase in strength as a result of the addition of the polyamide layers followed by hot pressing. For the NHC case the addition of the polyamide layers results in a decrease in strength, although after hot pressing the reduction is much smaller than without.

The analysis of variance can determine the influence factor on laminate quality and strength. For CAI strength, further examination focusing on the other factors which is not examined in this study is required.

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